

Determination of Vitamin C (Ascorbic Acid) in Orange Juices Product

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Abstract : This research describes a voltammetric approach to determine amounts of vitamin C (Ascorbic acid) in orange juice sample, using three screen printed electrode. The anodic currents of vitamin C were proportional to vitamin C concentration in the range of 0 - 10.0 mM with the limit of detection of 1.36 mM. The method was successfully employed with 2 μ L of the working solution dropped on the electrode surface. The proposed method was applied for the analysis of vitamin C in packed orange juice without sample purification or complexation of sample preparation step.

Keywords : ascorbic acid, vitamin C, juice, voltammetry

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